

Influence of Social Networking Sites on Body Image Dissatisfaction, Self Esteem and Other Co- Morbidities A Systematic Review of Psychological Research

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *With the quickly rising popularity of social media within the past decade, researchers have started to investigate the relationship between social media use and various psychological wellbeing variables. Given social media's similarity to traditional media, and the unique types of social comparisons that may occur on these platforms, body image has been a variable of interest. Thus, this study aims to evaluate the available literature on Body Image to provide a qualitative review of cross sectional research on this topic to provide clarification on the relationship between social media use, body image and self-esteem.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *The following databases were searched for empirical investigations of social media use, body image and self-esteem: Google scholar, Academia, Research Gate, PubMed and Web of Science. Constructs pertaining to social media platforms and their use, as well as the various components of body image and self-esteem were captured through keywords and the appropriate Boolean terms. In adherence to the PRISMA guidelines articles obtained through the database searches were first screened based on their titles, then abstracts, and then finally while considering the entire journal article.*

Findings/Result: *A mixed-model analysis of the literature indicates a small, positive, and significant relationship between social media use and body image disturbance. Type of social media use, body image dimension, country grouping, age, and ethnicity were all found to be significant moderators of this relationship.*

Originality/Value: *Strengths and limitations of this, literature review as well as future directions for this line of research are discussed.*

Paper Type: *Systematic Review of Literature.*

Keywords: Body image, Body concerns, Body satisfaction, Body dissatisfaction, Body Dimorphic Disorder; BDD Social media; Social networking; SNS. Self Esteem.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Body image issues are a common problem. In a society that promotes unrealistic body ideals, it is challenging to not get caught up in comparing oneself to these unrealistic standards. As a result, many individuals may experience depression, anxiety, anger and even self-loathing. In addition to affecting an individual's view of self, poor body image may also result in avoidance of social situations and may interfere with developing healthy social and romantic relationships [1]. Body image disturbance is on the rise in our society. These disturbances can lead to a lot of other health related issues and problems, like eating disorders, anorexia, depression etc. There have been a significant amount of studies, both western and Indian that, have been done to test the relationship between various forms of media and body image disturbances. One of the most intrinsic media element in a lot of people's lives today is the social media [2]. According to a 2016 report published by the Internet and Mobile Association of India (IAMAI), 66% of the total Internet users in urban India are active users of various social media platforms. Social media platforms influence a lot of facets in the users' life. In fact, many of the social media users turn to these platforms looking for inspiration on various counts. And one of the recent additions to this list of inspirations is 'fitness inspiration'. This is known as Fitspiration or simply Fitspo[3]. In the social media parlance, it is an online trend which aims to inspire viewers towards a healthier lifestyle. This is achieved by posting images of fit and 'thin'

looking people usually engaged in some form of exercise. The images can be accompanied by inspirational quotes and words. This has also given rise to a lot of related concepts like inspiration. But thin inspiration is a concept which is related to a lot of negative connotations. These promote the socio-cultural norms of ideal beauty[4]. This holds true for both women and men. For example, when viewing images of men, they “conform to only one body type that of a medium build with a high degree of muscularity. These can be a catalyst for increased BID, self-harm, eating disorders etc. Looking at this scenario the question that arises is this – Are social media platforms really helping to inspire people to be fit or are they simply becoming a tool that inadvertently lead to body image disturbances in people [5]. Significance of the problem Body Image disturbances are a fact of our life and have become a significant health issue for quite some time, especially for young adults and tweens. In the simplest of terms, Body Image is how one feels about their body [7]. And body image disturbances occur when a person feels negatively about their body and want to make significant (or sometimes even non-significant) changes to it. These changes could simply be 'routine behaviours' like changing the hair style, hair colouring, changing the dressing style, etc. [8]. But these could also be 'non-routine behaviours' like excessive exercise, crash dieting, taking supplements and even surgery. On the other hand, Social Media usage is on the rise. And, in comparison to traditional forms of media, like television and magazine, “social media permits for dynamic engagement.” What is seen and discussed there has a high impact on the users' life. And this is not necessarily always a positive impact. Social Media and the messages that one gets from them can lead to highly negative results in a person's life[9]. In such a state of affairs it becomes important to study social media exposure effects and people's perception leading to BID.

Unfortunately, individual with body image concerns usually do not have body satisfaction instead they are dissatisfied with their physical self [10]. The possible negative body image is obesity or overweight, exposure to ideal body image, attitudes of family and peers and unhealthy behaviours [11].

1.1 Definition

1.1.1. Body image is an individual perception of himself and his feelings towards his body. This term was first coined by Austrian neurologist and psychoanalyst Paul Schilder in his book ‘The Image and Appearance of the Human Body (1935)’. Literature on body image has been concerned with two aspects; Body perception and body satisfaction.[12].

1.1.2 Body perception is related to the physical aspect of their body. This is an individual’s assessment of the physical aspects (e.g. body weight, body shape, height etc.) of their body and the extent to which this assessment is accurate [13].

1.1.3 Social media (also referred to as social networking sites or SNSs) refers to online platforms, like Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter that allow users to create and share visual and textual content with other users [14].

1.1.4 Body Dimorphic Disorder (BDD) is a psychological disorder that involves a misperception of one or more body areas. Individuals with BDD perceive a defect or flaw in their appearance that is either very small or non-existent[15].

2. METHODOLOGY:

2.1 Search Strategy: In January 2021, the following databases were searched for empirical investigations of social media use and body image: Google scholar, Academia, Research Gate, PubMed and Web of Science. Both constructs pertaining to social media platforms and their use, as well as the various components of body image were captured through keywords and the appropriate Boolean terms. To capture social media use, the following search terms were used: body image, Body Dimorphic Disorder, Positive Body Image, Negative Body image, social media, social network, SNS, Facebook, Instagram, and review. Search terms used to capture the components of body image were: body image, body, appearance, dissatisfaction, satisfaction, eats, disorder, internalize, fat, thin, and muscular. Note that there were no time restrictions on this search regarding the earliest publication date of articles. In addition to this systematic search of journal articles, the reference lists of included articles and relevant review articles were also screened to identify any additional relevant articles for inclusion. Prominent authors in the field were also contacted for any additional working articles. Care was taken to include articles with over 500 citations irrespective of the time frame. Furthermore, a secondary search was conducted in July of 2021 to locate any additional articles published since the original search. Books on the topic body Image were also reviewed to understand the theoretical constructs, Definitions and validate and generally accepted assessment tools on Body image perceptions .these tools varied from Self-assessment to clinical assessment tools for the diagnosis or comorbid conditions like BDD , eating disorders ,sleeping disorder ,Vigorexia and the likes .In adherence to the PRISMA guidelines articles obtained through the database searches were first screened based on their titles, then abstracts, and then finally while considering the entire journal article [16]. At the initial title screening stage, articles were included if the title indicated that the study generally pertained to social media use and some aspect of body image. This process was

similarly followed at the abstract screening stage; however qualitative studies were excluded at this stage. Finally, the full-text articles of the accepted abstracts were screened for eligibility; articles were rejected at this stage if they did not include an independent measure of social media use, and/or an independent measure of overall body image – or a component of body image –, or did not have the information required to compute an effect size (e.g., qualitative studies). A comprehensive description of all inclusion and exclusion criteria is provided in the section below. The selection process is shown with the help of a flow chart in Figure 1.

2.2 Inclusion Criteria

In order to be included in the analysis, studies must have met the following inclusion criteria.

(a) Studies must have included an independent measure of social media use. The concept of social media use was broadly applied, where any aspect of social media use was accepted. The focus here was on use, meaning that any measure that captured a social media behaviour or activity that the users had to actively or passively engage in was included – for example, frequency of selfie posting.

(b) Studies must have included a measure assessing participants' positive or negative body image, or a component of their body image. This included measures assessing general body satisfaction or dissatisfaction (e.g., the appearance evaluation subscale of the Multidimensional Body-Self Relations Questionnaire).

(c) Studies must have used self-reported measures of social media use and body image; studies in which these constructs were measured in alternative ways (i.e., frequency of social media use was estimated by the researchers) were not included.

(d) Studies must have been cross-sectional in design. The majority of research conducted in this field fit this criterion; however, a small portion of experimental research exists as well.

(e) Article must have been written in English.

2.3 Sample-level characteristics.

While selecting the articles the sample level characteristics that were considered are Age, Gender, Ethnicity, Country grouping, Social Media Platform, Types of body image measure.

2.4 Measures

We grouped our review of the relevant studies into the following four categories of outcome variables: (a) body dissatisfaction/ BDD/ co-morbidities, (b) body self-consciousness/objectification/Self Esteem, (c) internalization of the thin ideal and drive for thinness, and (d) eating behaviours and beliefs (e) Social Media influence. In the category of body dissatisfaction we focused on measures that assess the evaluative component of body image, that is, satisfaction/dissatisfaction with the body.

Figure 1: Stages and process of selecting articles for review. (Source: Compiled by Author).

3. DISCUSSION

The literature investigating the relationship between social media use and body image is extensive, but does not offer consistent findings. Some correlational studies have found that social media use is associated with body image disturbance, while others have found that social media use is associated with a positive body image [17],[18]. Some studies have even found that there is no association between these two variables[19],[20] [21]. Despite these contradictory findings, the idea that social media is “bad” for body image seems to be pervasive in the media. When a research study finds that frequent social media use is linked to body image disturbance, it is often reported in the news, oftentimes in an exaggerated and fear-inducing manner [22]. The idea that social media is “bad” is also evident in the multiple body positivity movements present on social media[23]. The body positivity movement refers to any message delivered through various mediums that aims to challenge the societal ideals associated with appearance, beauty, and bodies, as well as to encourage self-acceptance [24]. Given the popularity of social media and the idealized content on social media, this movement has infiltrated social media platforms. Hash tags like “#effyourbeautystandards” [25], and “#allbodiesaregoodbodies” [26] attempt to challenge body ideals perpetuated on social media, and encourage social media users to engage in this challenge by posting content that promotes the acceptance of diverse body shapes and sizes [27]. These messages are pervasive, despite research and various theoretical frameworks suggesting that social media may be associated with an overall positive body image. Regardless, without a systematic culmination of these findings, the true relationship between social media use on body image remains unclear[28],[29].

Further, the current literature does not offer any consensus on potential moderators of the relationship between social media use and body image. Given that body image is considered a multidimensional concept, various structures have been suggested, however, [30] offer a four-component model that is frequently used and cited in the literature [31],[32]. *First* is the affective dimension, which includes how one feels about their body and the emotions associated with their evaluation of their body (e.g., appearance esteem). *Second* is the cognitive dimension, which includes beliefs that one holds about their body (e.g., internalization of the thin-ideal). *Third* is the behavioural dimension, which includes actions that one may engage in that are related to their own idea of their body (e.g., disordered eating). *Fourth* is the subjective satisfaction dimension, which captures one’s global satisfaction with their appearance and body[33] suggests that failing to consider these different dimensions separately could present an interpretive problem. That is, these dimensions may not necessarily be impacted by independent variables in the same way[34]. In fact, this was found to be true for body image and traditional media meta- analysis on the role of media images in body image concerns revealed different effect sizes for each dimension [35]. Thus, it is possible that social media use may be related to the different dimensions of body image in different ways[36].

This, therefore, leads to the conclusion that given the current state of the literature, a meta-analysis is warranted. A meta- analysis will provide consensus on the association between social media use and body image disturbance, if any. It will also provide an estimate of the strength of this relationship, and help to identify potential moderators of this relationship[37], [38]. Identifying potential moderators is a particularly important contribution since, as alluded to earlier, this relationship is likely to be different for different people (i.e., women, those who identify as Caucasian)[39], different types of social media use[40], (e.g., appearance-focused use), and for the different dimensions of body image [41],[42]. As this is a growing field of research, the current findings will help to shape future research.

3.1 Limitations

While this study of literature fills a gap in the body image literature, it is not without limitations. First, our analysis only included cross-sectional studies. This, of course, limited our ability to make causal claims. In other words, we are unable to say, based on this analysis, whether increased use of social media results in body image disturbance, or if pre-existing body image disturbance causes individuals to use social media at a higher frequency. Further, the estimate of a relationship provided in cross-sectional studies cannot take potential third variables into account. Thus, it’s possible that these estimates may be inflated or deflated because of some third variable that can explain both social media use and body image disturbance. A potential third variable may be self-esteem: Self-esteem has been linked to both social media use and body image

4. CONCLUSION

To conclude, the results of this literature analysis indicate that body image disturbance is associated with social media use. Despite the limitations discussed above, this review has several strengths. To the authors’ knowledge, this is the first comprehensive, review of this field of literature. This is in comparison to previous reviews that were focused on a single component of body image. As a result, this literature review provides an estimate of the strength of the relationship between social media use and body image disturbance that is more nuanced and comprehensive than those previously given. The magnitude of this effect was not as large as might have been predicted based on

previous research and common views amongst the public, which suggests that general social media use may not be as harmful as predicted for users in general. However, it may be particularly more harmful for certain users (e.g., younger users) who are engaging in certain behaviours (i.e., engaging in appearance-focused social media use). An interesting and important future direction to investigate would be to look at the interactions between variables like social media influence on the body image and self-esteem. For example, what body image outcome is associated with younger social media users engaging in appearance-focused use? A way to investigate this would be to conduct a meta-analysis of just studies investigating appearance-focused social media use. While many studies have investigated this specific type of social media use, more research needs to be done before an adequately powered meta-analysis can be conducted. This is an important future direction, as these findings could be used to develop interventions targeted at particular types of users who more frequently engage in certain types of social media behaviours. Additionally, social media is still a new technology, and we cannot be sure of the long-term effects it may have on users. Finally, the authors want to make it clear that this is an associative relationship; further research, of the experimental nature, is therefore needed to clarify the potential causal relationship

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